

Deployment of Context-Input-Process-Product (CIPP) on Evaluating Project LIGHT: An Embedded Exploratory-Explanatory Analysis on the Development of Reading Comprehension Skills Among Junior High School Learners

Mylene Solis
Cavite State University
mylenesolis2229@gmail.com

Date Submitted:
January 18, 2026

Date Accepted:
February 21, 2026

Date Published:
February 25, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.18765370

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated Project LIGHT as a reading intervention for junior high school students at Eastern Baco National High School. Specifically, it addressed: (1) the initial state of students' reading comprehension; (2) the effectiveness of Project LIGHT based on the Context-Input-Process-Product (CIPP) model; and (3) the outcomes and impact of the program on reading development. Conducted from January 2024 to May 2025, the study involved 60 students at frustration and instructional reading levels, identified through Phil-IRI assessments, and four English teachers. Thematic analysis guided by the CIPP model (Stufflebeam & Zhang, 2017) was used. Findings revealed that over 70% of students were below independent reading levels before the intervention. Context analysis confirmed

the urgent need for support. Project LIGHT proved effective by addressing academic and emotional reading challenges (Context), using quality materials and trained teachers (Input), implementing flexible and student-centered instruction (Process), and improving comprehension, vocabulary, and confidence (Product). Post-test scores and qualitative feedback indicated significant gains, although challenges persisted in Grade 7 and when session regularity declined. The study recommends institutionalizing structured reading programs like Project LIGHT, emphasizing early intervention, teacher training, consistent implementation, and family engagement. Continuous monitoring is essential to sustain progress. Longitudinal studies are suggested to assess long-term effects and scalability.

Keywords: *CIPP Model, thematic analysis, Project LIGHT, reading comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

Reading comprehension skills are fundamental for academic success across all subjects and grade levels. Effective comprehension allows students to understand and interpret text, make connections between ideas, and critically evaluate information. Without proficient reading comprehension skills, students may struggle to grasp the content presented in textbooks, academic articles, and other educational materials, hindering their ability to learn and excel academically.

Understanding complex texts is a central component of reading comprehension and a fundamental requirement for academic success. Complex texts often contain dense information, abstract ideas, and unfamiliar vocabulary, all of which demand higher-order cognitive processing from readers. The ability to engage with such texts enables learners to move beyond surface-level reading and toward deeper interpretation and understanding.

Proficient readers demonstrate the capacity to navigate challenging texts by identifying key information and determining main ideas. They are able to recognize relationships among concepts, distinguish relevant from irrelevant details, and follow the logical structure of a text. These skills allow readers to build coherent mental representations of what they read, which is essential for meaningful comprehension.

In addition, skilled readers synthesize information across sentences and paragraphs to construct overall meaning. This process involves integrating prior knowledge with textual information and making inferences that are not explicitly stated. As noted by Hiebert and Pearson (2020), effective readers engage deeply with texts, recognize distinctions within ideas, and draw well-founded conclusions based on textual evidence.

Despite the importance of these skills, many junior high school students continue to experience difficulties in reading comprehension. Such challenges may hinder their academic performance across subject areas, as reading serves as a foundation for learning in most disciplines. Consequently, there is a growing need for structured and specific interventions that can support struggling readers in developing these essential competencies.

In response to this need, various reading interventions have been designed to enhance comprehension skills among adolescents, including Project LIGHT. Project LIGHT, which stands for *Learning to Read with Confidence Through Intensive Implementation of Reading Intervention Program among Growing Number of Struggling Readers in Junior High School by Utilizing Localized and Contextualized Texts*, is a comprehensive initiative aimed at improving students' reading abilities. By addressing the complex nature of reading comprehension through mixed-method research, Project LIGHT and similar programs contribute significantly to fostering learners' confidence, engagement, and overall academic success.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension skills play a fundamental role in academic achievement across subjects and grade levels. Proficient comprehension enables students to understand, interpret, and critically analyze textual information, which is essential for academic tasks such as writing, problem-solving, and content-area learning (Guthrie et al., 2019). As students' progress to junior high school, reading demands increase in complexity, requiring higher-level cognitive processing and strategic engagement with texts.

Reading comprehension is a multidimensional cognitive process that involves decoding, vocabulary knowledge, background knowledge, inference-making, and metacognitive regulation. According to the construction–integration model, readers actively construct meaning by integrating textual information with prior knowledge and continuously refining their understanding (Kintsch, 2013). Deficiencies in any of these components may hinder comprehension, particularly among adolescent readers.

Adolescent learners face distinct challenges in reading comprehension due to increased exposure to complex academic texts and reduced instructional emphasis on reading beyond the primary grades. Many students enter junior high school without fully developed comprehension strategies, leading to difficulties in understanding content-area texts (Biancarosa & Snow, 2006). These challenges highlight the necessity of sustained literacy instruction at the secondary level.

In response, reading comprehension interventions have been developed to support students in acquiring the skills and strategies necessary for effective reading. These interventions encompass a wide range of instructional approaches informed by theoretical frameworks and empirical research (Erya & Pustaka, 2021). Effective interventions are designed to address diverse learner needs through structured instruction, scaffolding, and strategy application (Duke & Pearson, 2012).

One widely used approach in comprehension interventions is explicit instruction. This approach involves directly teaching comprehension strategies such as activating prior knowledge, monitoring understanding, making inferences, and summarizing texts (Pressley et al., 2010). Teachers model strategy use, provide guided practice, and gradually transfer responsibility to students. Research indicates that explicit instruction is particularly effective for struggling readers and English language learners due to its systematic and structured nature (Vaughn & Linan-Thompson, 2013).

Metacognitive strategy instruction is closely aligned with explicit instruction and plays a vital role in reading comprehension development. Metacognition allows students to reflect on their understanding, identify comprehension breakdowns, and apply appropriate strategies to resolve difficulties. Studies have shown that learners who receive metacognitive strategy instruction demonstrate improved comprehension and greater autonomy as readers (Baker & Beall, 2009; Zimmerman, 2008).

Vocabulary knowledge is another critical factor influencing reading comprehension, especially in secondary education where texts contain abstract and discipline-specific terms. Limited vocabulary can restrict students' ability to construct meaning from texts. Integrating explicit vocabulary instruction within comprehension interventions has been found to significantly enhance students' understanding of complex texts (Nagy & Townsend, 2012; Perfetti & Stafura, 2014).

The success of reading comprehension programs depends heavily on teacher competence and professional preparation. Teachers require comprehensive training and sustained professional development to implement interventions effectively. Research emphasizes the importance of equipping educators with evidence-based instructional practices, including explicit strategy instruction and differentiated teaching methods (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Well-designed professional development programs strengthen teachers' instructional capacity and positively influence student learning outcomes.

Instructional design also plays a critical role in the effectiveness of reading comprehension interventions. Effective programs incorporate scaffolded instruction, formative assessment, and opportunities for independent practice. Ongoing assessment and progress monitoring allow teachers to evaluate students' comprehension development and provide timely, distinct support (Pressley et al., 2010; Fuchs & Fuchs, 2016).

Student motivation and engagement are significant predictors of success in reading comprehension programs. Motivated students are more likely to engage actively with texts, apply comprehension strategies, and persist in challenging reading tasks (Guthrie et al., 2019). Instructional practices that provide choice, meaningful reading activities, and collaborative discussions foster intrinsic motivation and positive reading identities (Gambrell, 2011).

Culturally relevant and contextualized reading materials further enhance comprehension and engagement. When texts reflect students' cultural backgrounds, experiences, and local contexts, learners are more likely to connect with the material and construct meaning effectively. Research supports the use of culturally responsive literacy instruction to promote equity and inclusivity in reading education (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 2014).

Family and community involvement also contribute significantly to students' reading comprehension development. Collaborative partnerships between schools, families, and communities reinforce literacy practices beyond the classroom. Home-based reading activities, such as shared reading and discussions, support comprehension development and foster positive reading habits (Epstein et al., 2002; Sénéchal & LeFevre, 2012).

An important consideration in evaluating reading comprehension interventions is the transferability of acquired skills to other academic and real-world contexts. Students who develop proficiency in comprehension strategies are better equipped to engage with texts across disciplines and genres (Pressley et al., 2010). Research suggests that explicit and contextualized instruction enhances students' ability to transfer comprehension skills beyond instructional settings (Rosenshine & Meister, 1994; Shanahan et al., 2010).

Overall, strong reading comprehension skills have long-term implications for students' academic success and educational attainment. Proficient readers are more likely to complete secondary education and pursue higher education or vocational pathways (Lesaux & Marietta, 2012). Given these outcomes, there is a critical need to examine the effectiveness of reading comprehension interventions in junior high school contexts. Investigating programs such as Project LIGHT contributes to the growing body of research on adolescent literacy and informs evidence-based practices that support struggling readers.

METHODS

This study used an embedded mixed method research design, particularly the exploratory-explanatory method of research. The study involved 4 English teachers who have used Project LIGHT as a reading intervention and 60 frustration and instructional level readers. The researcher-made instrument was subjected to validation by experts. Frequency count and thematic analysis were used to analyze the data.

Figure 1. CIPP Model

The Context-Input-Process-Product (CIPP) model was used in this study. The research followed the model above in conducting the thematic analysis of Project LIGHT as a reading intervention program. Context Evaluation involved setting of goals such as identifying the beneficiaries, needs, resources, problems, background, and environment. Input Evaluation involved the planning stage such as determining the stakeholders, strategies, budget, and coverage. Process Evaluation involves taking actions such as developing, implementing, monitoring, and getting feedback. Lastly, Product Evaluation involves identifying the outcomes such as impact, effectiveness, sustainability, and adjustment pertinent to Project LIGHT (Stufflebeam and Zhang, 2017).

After the thematic analysis of each component of Project LIGHT, an overall analysis will be done to interweave all of the critical analyses of each component.

RESULTS

Reading Comprehension as a Persistent Struggle

Across all teacher participants, a common observation—supported by Phil-IRI results—was that students consistently entered junior high school with significant difficulties in reading comprehension. Teacher 1 noted that students struggled with identifying main ideas and supporting details, stressing a weakness in both literal and inferential comprehension. Teacher 3 reinforced this view by pointing out that

“they cannot easily understand the meaning of the words, even some of the basic words.” These statements reflect a foundational vocabulary gap and an underdeveloped capacity for meaning-making, which are essential for navigating complex academic texts. This suggests that reading instruction should move beyond decoding and explicitly aim comprehension strategies early in junior high school. Programs like Project LIGHT address this gap by prioritizing structured and specific interventions focused on comprehension.

Socio-Economic Influences on Reading Behavior

Teachers identified socio-economic factors as a major influence on students’ reading habits and motivation. Teacher 2 explained that “most students don’t have anyone at home who can help them read or explain things.” Teacher 3 added that “many parents work until late and there’s no one to support reading at home.” These conditions result in limited reading practice and affect students’ exposure to text-rich environments outside school. The implication here is the need to design school-based interventions that do not solely rely on home reinforcement. While family involvement should be encouraged, schools must compensate through extended reading sessions, access to take-home reading materials, and collaboration with local communities.

Lack of Metacognitive Awareness and Self-Regulation

A recurring theme was the absence of metacognitive strategies among students. Teacher 4 observed, “they read without knowing if they understood anything. If you ask questions, they get lost.” Students lacked awareness of their comprehension and did not engage in self-checking or repair strategies. This suggests that reading instruction must include teaching students how to monitor their understanding, apply fix-up strategies, and reflect on their learning. Embedding metacognitive instruction across subjects can help develop independent and strategic readers.

Infrastructural and Logistical Constraints

Teachers also cited limitations in time and space allocated for reading. As Teacher 2 described, “we don’t have a reading center or even just a quiet place to let them read.” Literacy activities had to be “squeezed into free time,” often competing with core subjects. These constraints directly limit the depth and consistency of reading interventions. This shows the need for school leadership to institutionalize reading periods, allocate reading-friendly spaces, and treat literacy instruction as integral—not supplementary—to the curriculum.

Cultural and Linguistic Diversity

Students’ difficulty engaging with culturally unfamiliar texts also emerged as a significant barrier. Teacher 1 noted, “they’re confused by foreign names or settings. It feels far from their world.” This

disconnect often led to disengagement and surface-level understanding. The implication is clear: reading materials must be localized and culturally relevant. When students see their own lives reflected in texts, comprehension and motivation improve. Project LIGHT's use of localized materials effectively addressed this concern and should serve as a model for future instructional design.

Emotional Readiness and Self-Perception

Students themselves expressed emotional barriers to reading. Student 8 shared, "I get scared to read in front of others. I feel embarrassed when I make mistakes." Similarly, Student 10 said, "I think I'm a weak reader, and sometimes I don't even want to try." These comments reveal how affective factors such as fear, anxiety, and low self-esteem can suppress reading participation and persistence. Reading programs must cultivate safe, supportive learning environments where students feel empowered to take risks. Emotional scaffolding—such as praise, peer support, and gradual exposure to public reading—can significantly boost students' willingness to engage.

Evaluation of Project LIGHT Using the CIPP Model

Context Evaluation: Shared Perception of Urgency and Need

Both teachers and students recognized the critical need for reading intervention within the school context. Teacher 1 remarked, "Without Project LIGHT, most of our students would stay behind," emphasizing the perceived urgency to address persistent literacy gaps. Students echoed this sentiment; Student 10 shared, "Before this, I was afraid of reading. Now I'm trying, and it's not that bad," illustrating how the program directly addressed students' anxieties and fostered a willingness to engage with texts.

This shared acknowledgment of literacy challenges and the value of structured support validated the implementation of Project LIGHT. When both teachers and learners perceive the importance and relevance of an intervention, engagement and commitment to the program naturally increase. Such alignment between stakeholder perception and program goals enhances the likelihood of successful outcomes and sustained participation.

Furthermore, involving teachers and students in the planning and evaluation processes shows the importance of inclusive program design. When learners' experiences and teachers' insights inform instructional materials, strategies, and pacing, interventions are more likely to meet actual needs, remain contextually appropriate, and foster a sense of shared ownership. This approach reinforces the principle that literacy programs are most effective when they are collaboratively grounded in the lived realities of their intended beneficiaries.

Input Evaluation: Contextualized Materials and Capacity Building

Teachers carefully designed instructional materials to reflect students' lives, experiences, and cultural contexts. Teacher 3 noted, "We used stories about barangays, fiestas, even local myths. They loved it because it felt familiar," illustrating how culturally and locally relevant content increases engagement and motivation. By connecting reading materials to students' personal and community experiences, the program helped learners see the relevance of literacy to their own lives, fostering deeper comprehension and meaningful interaction with texts.

In addition to contextualized materials, teacher training played a critical role in the program's effectiveness. Teacher 2 explained, "We were trained to use Phil-IRI and design tasks for frustration, instructional, and independent readers," highlighting the systematic approach to assessing student needs and grouping learners according to reading levels. This capacity-building enabled teachers to design instruction, provide differentiated support, and ensure that all students could progress at an appropriate pace.

The combination of localized content and well-prepared teachers proved essential for enhancing both engagement and learning outcomes. By integrating culturally meaningful texts with structured teacher support, Project LIGHT created an environment where students were motivated to participate, confident in their abilities, and able to apply comprehension strategies effectively. These findings explain the importance of investing in both instructional resources and teacher capacity to maximize the impact of literacy interventions in junior high school contexts.

Multimodal Resources and Home Involvement

The use of diverse instructional formats, including video read-alongs, digital texts, and interactive materials, played a significant role in supporting students' comprehension and engagement. Student 9 shared, "Watching the video first helped me understand the story better before reading," illustrating how multimodal resources can scaffold understanding and provide multiple entry points for learners. These strategies help bridge gaps for students who may struggle with decoding or abstract concepts, making texts more accessible and meaningful.

Home involvement further amplified the gains achieved in school. Student 7 noted, "I practice reading with my mom now. She helps me pronounce hard words," highlighting how parental engagement reinforces classroom learning. When students receive support both at school and at home, reading practice becomes more consistent, and comprehension skills are strengthened. However, the program also recognized the need for equity: not all students have the same level of family support. Therefore, literacy interventions should encourage home-based reinforcement while providing alternative strategies—such as peer reading, mentoring, or school-based reading clubs—to ensure that all learners benefit regardless of family circumstances.

This dual focus on multimodal resources and home engagement stresses the importance of a holistic approach to literacy instruction. Programs that integrate technology, diverse media, and supportive home environments can enhance comprehension, motivation, and learner confidence. By addressing both in-school and out-of-school literacy experiences, interventions like Project LIGHT create stronger and sustainable pathways for reading development, fostering lifelong literacy habits.

Process Evaluation: Implementation and Student Growth

Teachers employed interactive and varied instructional strategies, including storytelling, phonics games, and paired reading, to engage students meaningfully. Teacher 1 observed, “These activities made them look forward to sessions,” highlighting the motivational impact of interactive approaches. Student 9 shared, “At first I just listened, but now I read too. It’s fun,” demonstrating increased participation and enjoyment. These reflections indicate a shift from passive reception of information to active engagement, where students take ownership of their learning and participate confidently in literacy activities.

The integration of emotionally engaging and student-centered strategies not only increased motivation but also supported the development of comprehension skills in a natural and enjoyable context. By combining cognitive skill-building with interactive and playful learning, teachers helped students internalize reading strategies while fostering positive attitudes toward reading. This process highlights the importance of designing literacy programs that are responsive to students’ interests and emotional needs, reinforcing the connection between engagement, skill development, and sustained reading growth.

Implementation Challenges and Flexibility

Teachers encountered challenges related to time, space, and competing instructional priorities. Teacher 4 explained, “Sometimes we had to conduct sessions during lunch or in the corridor,” highlighting the logistical constraints faced during program implementation. Despite these limitations, teachers demonstrated adaptability, creativity, and commitment, ensuring that sessions continued effectively. Their resourcefulness shows the critical role of teacher initiative in maintaining program momentum even under suboptimal conditions.

These experiences point to the necessity of strong institutional support to reduce logistical barriers and facilitate program sustainability. Dedicated scheduling, access to appropriate learning spaces, and flexible allocation of resources are essential for continuity and scalability. Moreover, administrative encouragement and recognition of teacher efforts can enhance morale, increase fidelity to the program design, and support long-term implementation. Addressing these factors ensures that interventions like Project LIGHT can maintain both instructional quality and positive student outcomes over time.

Product Evaluation: Learning Gains and Behavioral Shifts

Teachers reported measurable gains in students' reading performance and self-assurance following the implementation of Project LIGHT. Teacher 2 stated, "We saw real growth—not just in test scores, but in how they approached texts," highlighting changes in both achievement and reading behavior. Student 8 similarly shared, "Now, I can read faster and understand more—even if it's long," indicating improved fluency and comprehension. These gains suggest that the program supported not only skill acquisition but also positive shifts in students' attitudes toward reading.

Notably, the improvements extended beyond English classes. Teacher 4 observed transfer effects in content-based subjects such as Araling Panlipunan, where students demonstrated better understanding of texts and increased participation. This cross-curricular impact indicates that enhanced reading competence enables students to access and process academic content more effectively across disciplines. The observed behavioral shifts—greater confidence, persistence, and engagement—show the value of reading interventions as foundational academic supports rather than isolated remedial programs.

Skill Development and Motivation

Students developed specific comprehension strategies such as summarizing texts and using context clues to infer meaning. Student 9 explained, "I didn't know how to guess meanings before, but now I try using the words around it," while Student 10 shared, "I can now tell the story after reading it." These responses indicate the development of deeper comprehension skills and growing independence in reading. The ability to retell texts and infer word meanings suggests that students are moving beyond surface-level understanding toward more strategic and purposeful reading.

The emergence of these skills reflects the effectiveness of scaffolded instruction in equipping learners with transferable cognitive strategies. As students gain confidence in applying these strategies independently, they become more motivated to engage with increasingly complex texts. Sustained programs like Project LIGHT not only strengthen foundational reading skills but also cultivate enduring learning habits, self-regulation, and intrinsic motivation. These outcomes suggest that long-term, strategy-focused literacy interventions can support students in becoming autonomous readers who are better prepared to meet academic challenges beyond the classroom.

DISCUSSION

Teachers observed a notable shift from surface-level guessing to deeper comprehension and more thoughtful responses among students. Teacher 2 remarked, "Before, they would just pick random answers or guess. Now, they try to explain why they chose something." Similarly, Teacher 5 shared, "They're not just reading for the sake of finishing. They ask questions, they connect ideas." These reflections suggest the emergence of analytical reading skills, which mark a significant development from students' pre-intervention behavior. The implication is that interventions like Project LIGHT can scaffold learners from passive decoding to active meaning-making, a shift that is critical for academic success across content areas where comprehension underpins learning.

This transition from surface-level reading to deeper comprehension reflects the development of metacognitive awareness among students. As learners begin to justify answers, ask questions, and connect ideas, they demonstrate growing control over comprehension strategies such as monitoring understanding and evaluating meaning. Such behaviors indicate that students are no longer merely responding to text but are engaging in reflective and purposeful reading. This development supports the notion that structured reading interventions can foster higher-order thinking skills, particularly when students are guided to articulate their reasoning and reflect on their reading processes.

Teachers also reported increased student enthusiasm and engagement during reading sessions. According to Teacher 1, “They now look forward to reading time. Some even remind me if I forget to start the session.” Teacher 3 added, “They used to avoid eye contact when asked to read. Now, they raise their hands.” This change signifies not only improved motivation but also a growing sense of ownership over the learning process. When reading becomes a regular and enjoyable activity rather than a source of fear or boredom, students are more likely to sustain their literacy development over time. This shows the importance of embedding reading into daily routines and positioning it as an emotionally rewarding experience.

The observed increase in engagement also suggests a shift in classroom culture toward one that values participation and risk-taking. Students’ willingness to volunteer and remind teachers about reading sessions reflects increased confidence and a sense of belonging within the learning environment. Such an atmosphere is essential for struggling readers, as it reduces fear of failure and encourages experimentation with new strategies. These findings imply that literacy interventions are most effective when they are implemented within supportive, non-threatening classroom contexts that prioritize encouragement and consistency.

Moreover, post-program assessments demonstrated improvements not only in English reading comprehension but also in content-based subjects such as Araling Panlipunan and Science. Teacher 4 emphasized, “They understood word problems better in Science, and they started participating in Araling Panlipunan discussions.” Teacher 6 added, “I saw improvement in how they answered comprehension questions—more complete, more thoughtful.” This cross-disciplinary impact reinforces the centrality of reading skills in overall academic achievement. It suggests that reading proficiency functions as a foundational academic skill that enables learners to access and engage meaningfully with content across the curriculum.

The transfer of reading skills to other subject areas indicates that students were able to generalize comprehension strategies beyond the language classroom. Skills such as identifying main ideas, making inferences, and interpreting questions appear to have supported students’ understanding of informational and expository texts. This finding highlights the broader academic value of literacy interventions and supports the integration of reading instruction across subject areas rather than limiting it to English classes alone.

The emotional transformation among students was evident in their newfound confidence during reading activities. Student 7 shared, “Before, I would pretend to be busy so I won’t be called. Now, I want to try reading.” Student 10 added, “Even if I make mistakes, I still read aloud. It’s okay now.” These comments reveal the program’s success in reducing reading anxiety and promoting emotional resilience. Increased confidence not only supports literacy development but also contributes to a more positive academic self-concept, which is essential for sustained learning.

This growth in emotional readiness suggests that Project LIGHT created a psychologically safe environment where mistakes were treated as part of the learning process. By normalizing struggle and encouraging effort, the program helped students develop resilience and perseverance. Such affective gains are particularly important for adolescent learners who may carry long-standing negative experiences with reading. Addressing emotional barriers alongside cognitive skills appears to be a key factor in the program's effectiveness.

Several students indicated that their interest in reading extended beyond the classroom. Student 8 shared, "I started reading books and even Wattpad stories at home." Student 9 echoed this by saying, "Sometimes I borrow my sister's books or read articles online now." These responses reflect a transformation in students' reading identity—from reading as an academic requirement to reading as a personally meaningful activity. Voluntary engagement in reading outside school suggests internalization of literacy habits and intrinsic motivation.

This extension of reading practices into students' personal lives shows the sustainability of the program's impact. When learners independently seek reading opportunities, it signals long-term engagement that goes beyond program implementation. These findings highlight the importance of ensuring continued access to reading materials and encouraging reading-rich environments both in school and at home to maintain and extend literacy gains.

Students also reported progress in specific comprehension skills such as summarizing, identifying main ideas, and using context clues. Student 10 reflected, "I can now tell the story in my own words after reading." Student 9 added, "If I don't understand a word, I try to guess what it means using the sentence." These behaviors indicate the development of transferable comprehension strategies and higher-order thinking skills. The emergence of these strategies among previously struggling readers demonstrates the effectiveness of scaffolded, strategy-focused instruction.

The ability to articulate understanding and apply strategies independently suggests that students are developing cognitive tools that support lifelong learning. These skills enable learners to approach unfamiliar texts with greater confidence and autonomy. The findings imply that sustained literacy programs should continue to emphasize strategy instruction to equip students with adaptable skills applicable across academic and real-world contexts.

In sum, the outcomes and impacts of Project LIGHT demonstrate that structured, contextualized, and student-centered reading interventions can generate meaningful improvements in both the cognitive and affective domains of literacy. Thematic findings revealed enhanced reading comprehension, increased student engagement, improved performance across subjects, and strengthened confidence and motivation. These gains were supported by observable behavioral changes and qualitative evidence from both teachers and students. Importantly, the benefits extended beyond English classes, showing the cross-curricular value of reading proficiency. Collectively, these findings suggest that sustainable and inclusive reading interventions like Project LIGHT can serve as effective models for addressing literacy gaps and fostering holistic academic development in junior high school settings.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Project LIGHT effectively addressed critical reading comprehension gaps among junior high school students by responding to clearly identified academic and emotional needs. Prior to its implementation, Phil-IRI pre-test results indicated that more than 70% of students were performing below the independent reading level, confirming widespread difficulties in vocabulary development, inference-making, and identification of main ideas. These findings highlighted the urgent need for a structured and contextually relevant reading intervention.

Through the application of the CIPP Evaluation Model, Project LIGHT demonstrated strong contextual relevance and responsiveness to these challenges. The alignment of program objectives with learners' needs, coupled with the use of localized and contextualized texts, varied instructional resources, and specific teacher support, contributed to notable improvements in students' reading comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, fluency, and overall learner confidence. Teachers' adaptability in implementing instructional strategies and students' increased motivation, engagement, and classroom participation reflected growth in both cognitive and affective domains.

Despite these positive outcomes, certain implementation-related concerns emerged. Sustaining teacher motivation, managing instructional workload, and ensuring consistent scheduling of intervention sessions remained areas requiring further attention. These challenges suggest that program effectiveness is influenced not only by instructional design but also by institutional and organizational support structures.

To strengthen and sustain the gains achieved through Project LIGHT, enhanced institutional support is recommended. This includes more systematic scheduling of intervention sessions, sufficient preparation time for teachers, and continuous professional development focused on literacy instruction and learner engagement. Establishing mechanisms to support teacher motivation—such as workload management, recognition of instructional efforts, and opportunities for peer collaboration—may further improve program sustainability and effectiveness.

Moreover, continuous monitoring and evaluation using the CIPP framework can ensure that the program remains responsive to evolving learner needs and implementation contexts. Extending structured reading interventions to lower grade levels and integrating emotional and motivational components into reading instruction may further reinforce literacy development. Collectively, these measures can promote sustained improvements in reading comprehension and contribute to the development of long-term academic resilience among learners.

IMPLICATIONS

The results of Project LIGHT have significant implications for literacy instruction and program implementation in junior high schools. The demonstrated improvement in students' reading comprehension, confidence, and motivation shows the importance of integrating both academic and affective support within literacy interventions. Effective reading development is not limited to cognitive skill acquisition alone; it also involves nurturing learners' self-efficacy, engagement, and positive reading identities.

Schools should recognize that successful reading programs require more than contextualized instructional materials and competent teachers. Consistent program scheduling, strong institutional support, adequate resources, and attention to teacher workload and well-being are equally critical to sustaining

effective implementation. When these structural and human factors are addressed, interventions are more likely to achieve meaningful and lasting outcomes.

The success of Project LIGHT demonstrates the value of sustained, evidence-based, and learner-centered approaches that align instructional practices with students' diverse literacy needs. Moreover, the findings suggest that embedding structured reading interventions early in secondary education can contribute to long-term academic resilience, improved performance across content areas, and the development of a school-wide culture that values and promotes reading across grade levels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors express their gratitude to Romblon State University – Graduate Education and Professional Studies (GEPS) for their support during the conduct of this study. The authors also express gratitude to the City Division of Bacoor, Cavite Province for hosting the authors during the conduct of the study.

REREFERENCES

- Baker, L., & Beall, L. C. (2009). Metacognitive processes and reading comprehension. In S. E. Israel & G. G. Duffy (Eds.), *Handbook of research on reading comprehension* (pp. 373–388). Routledge.
- Biancarosa, G., & Snow, C. E. (2006). Reading next—A vision for action and research in middle and high school literacy: A report from Carnegie Corporation of New York. *Alliance for Excellent Education*.
- Connor, C. M., Morrison, F. J., Fishman, B. J., Schatschneider, C., & Underwood, P. (2014). Algorithm-guided individualized reading instruction. *Science*, 345(6193), 1204–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1254980>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyler, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2017). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Desimone, L. M., & Garet, M. S. (2015). Best practices in teachers' professional development in the United States. *Psychology, Society, & Education*, 7(3), 252–263.
- Duke, N. K., & Cartwright, K. B. (2021). The science of reading progresses: Communicating advances beyond the simple view of reading. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 56(S1), S25–S44. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.411>
- Duke, N. K., & Pearson, P. D. (2012). Effective practices for developing reading comprehension. In A. E. Farstrup & S. J. Samuels (Eds.), *What research has to say about reading instruction* (4th ed., pp. 205–242). International Reading Association.
- Epstein, J. L., Sanders, M. G., Simon, B. S., Salinas, K. C., Jansorn, N. R., & Van Voorhis, F. L. (2002). *School, family, and community partnerships: Your handbook for action* (2nd ed.). Corwin Press.
- Erya, R., & Pustika, R. (2021). Students' reading comprehension difficulties and strategies. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 2(2), 1–9.
- Fuchs, D., & Fuchs, L. S. (2016). Critique of the National Evaluation of Response to Intervention: A case for simpler frameworks. *Exceptional Children*, 82(3), 255–268. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0014402915626930>
- Gambrell, L. B. (2011). Seven rules of engagement: What's most important to know about motivation to read. *The Reading Teacher*, 65(3), 172–178. <https://doi.org/10.1002/TRTR.01024>
- Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice* (3rd ed.). Teachers College Press.
- Guthrie, J. T., Klauda, S. L., & Ho, A. N. (2019). Modeling the relationships among reading instruction, motivation, engagement, and achievement. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 48(1), 9–26. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rrq.035>
- Kintsch, W. (2013). *The construction–integration model of text comprehension*. Psychology Press.

- Ladson-Billings, G. (2014). *Culturally relevant pedagogy 2.0: A.k.a. the remix*. Harvard Educational Review, 84(1), 74–84.
- Lesaux, N. K., & Marietta, S. H. (2012). Adolescent literacy: Addressing the needs of students in grades 4–12. *Future of Children*, 22(2), 17–40.
- McKeown, M. G., Beck, I. L., & Blake, R. G. (2009). Rethinking reading comprehension instruction: A comparison of instruction for strategies and content approaches. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 44(3), 218–253. <https://doi.org/10.1598/RRQ.44.3.1>
- Nagy, W., & Townsend, D. (2012). Words as tools: Learning academic vocabulary as language acquisition. *Reading Research Quarterly*, 47(1), 91–108. <https://doi.org/10.1002/RRQ.011>
- Perfetti, C. A., & Stafura, J. (2014). Word knowledge in a theory of reading comprehension. *Scientific Studies of Reading*, 18(1), 22–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888438.2013.827687>
- Pressley, M., Afflerbach, P., Verducci, J., Lycett, M., & Echevarria, M. (2010). Verbal protocols of reading: The nature of constructively responsive reading. *Routledge*.
- Rosenshine, B., & Meister, C. (1994). Reciprocal teaching: A review of the research. *Review of Educational Research*, 64(4), 479–530.
- Sénéchal, M., & LeFevre, J. A. (2012). Continuity and change in the home literacy environment as predictors of growth in vocabulary and reading. *Child Development*, 83(3), 1206–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2012.01770.x>
- Shanahan, T., Shanahan, C., & Mischia, C. (2010). Analysis of expert readers in three disciplines: History, mathematics, and chemistry. *Journal of Literacy Research*, 42(1), 44–71.
- Snow, C. E. (2002). *Reading for understanding: Toward an R&D program in reading comprehension*. RAND Corporation.
- Vaughn, S., & Linan-Thompson, S. (2013). What is special about special education for students with learning disabilities? *The Journal of Special Education*, 47(2), 66–76.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2008). Investigating self-regulation and motivation: Historical background, methodological developments, and future prospects. *American Educational Research Journal*, 45(1), 166–183.